

* Onoriu Colăcel

Faculty of Letters and Communication Sciences
Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava
13 Universității Street, 720229 Suceava, Romania
e-mail: onoriucolacel@litere.usv.ro

CULTURAL DIFFUSION AND THE MEDIA IMPACT OF LABOR MIGRATION: BRITISH-ROMANIAN PERSPECTIVES

Abstract

The representation of im(e)migration in Romanian-language cultures is undergoing dramatic change. Migration in the UK, working knowledge of English, and the ready availability of online English-language news to (young and adult) Romanian audiences are significant means for diffusing a culture of anxiety about labor migration; such views have become gradually embedded in Romanian media. In particular, British tabloid reports on migration have shaped a social imaginary on emigration (and immigration), contributing to the articulation of local media stories and mainstream cultural meanings among Romanian-speaking audiences. Labor migration, as either glamorized or denounced, is framed in culturally conditioned, non-empirical terms, otherwise foreign to contexts such as Romania (still an emigration country). A comparative case study between English and Romanian-language media, that aims to show mostly linear, one-way effects on Romanian news and opinion, is proposed.

Keywords: cultural diffusion, labor migration, media narratives, Romania, Great Britain

1. Introduction

A cross-national perspective on the media coverage of topical issues, such as European migration flows, can suggest ways in which news and opinion function as narratives of cultural diffusion. They secure “the transmission of cultural elements from one society or cultural group to another” (Andersen et al., 2014: 60). Mainstream reporting on labor immigration (from small to big media market countries) is proving to be a significant conduit for the dissemination of “British tabloid logic” (Cross, 2014: 204) in Romania. As local migration in the United Kingdom has been covered by both British and Romanian media, a contrastive reading can be conducive to a better understanding of cultural convergence across Europe (rather than in the European Union, now that the UK finds itself outside the EU). Ideas about labor migration in the UK, commonly associated with the so-called populist media, have spread to Romanian news and opinion, mainly through adaptation and translation. Both are changing the perception of emigration and immigration among Romanian-speaking audiences: English-language reports on migration have shaped a social imaginary on im(e)migration by contributing to the articulation of local narratives, cultural meanings, and stereotypical practices that impact national self-identification discourses.

Although the media image of the Romanians living in Great Britain is much talked of, the coverage of contentious issues related to immigration is denying the public a comprehensive view of migration. Romanian-language media commonly conflate the mass emigration of highly educated professionals with un/low-skilled migrants even though “the impact of migration on the construction of Romania’s country image” (Dolea, 2018) is a concern in the Romanian academe as well. Romanian immigration has often been in the UK media spotlight. There is consensus that English-language populist media heap scorn on the Romanian poor, with notions of cosmopolitanism and the East-West

* Onoriu Colăcel is Professor of English at Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava, Romania, where he teaches literature and culture. His main research interests are concerned with postcolonial studies, cultural memory and patterns of self-identification in literature, media and popular culture. He has authored four books (e.g., *Postcolonial Readings of Romanian Identity Narratives*, 2015, and *The Romanian Cinema of Nationalism. Historical Films as Propaganda and Spectacle*, 2018) and has co-edited (with Anastasiya Astapova, Corneliu Pintilescu and Tamás Scheibner) *Conspiracy Theories in Eastern Europe: Tropes and Trends* (2021).

divide firmly in place as this seems taken for granted among the Romanians themselves (Andreouli et al., 2019). Discriminated against when times get hard (Pantiru, 2014), particularly the Bulgarians and the Romanians (Balch et al., 2016) are thought to be “stealing jobs and benefits” (Pencheva, 2020). Ultimately, low-status workers play a significant role in projecting Romanian identity for both international and, gradually more, home audiences.

Free online news platforms, mastery or working knowledge of English as a foreign language, and the large community of Romanians living in the UK, all help circulate the perspective of English-language news and opinion on immigration in the media networks of Romania, still an emigration country. The degree to which the local media has come to frame emigration as a threat to Romania and its people, much like the British tabloid press, is understudied. This gives insight into the way reporting frames, common in the big media markets of the English-speaking world, have gained traction across peripheral ones (i.e., the Romanian one).

2. Literature Review and Background

Literature in English has long shown that the framing of the Romanians in the “British press” (Mădroane, 2012) had everything to do with their arrival in the UK, only made possible by Romania’s EU accession. As one of the largest groups among the “EU nationals in the UK, after Brexit” (Vathi and Trandafoiu, 2020), the Romanian communities have come to a new awareness of themselves, both at home and abroad, through their own (and other’s) media discourses. Considering the long-time coverage of post-communist im(e)migration by the Romanian media, research in the field has highlighted a dynamic of the dominant representations of migrants (Beciu et al., 2017) in British news (Mădroane, 2018) and, increasingly, at home. Particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, their images in the mainstream media became more diversified. As the crisis continued, a growing body of English-language literature on Romanian immigration moved beyond making the case for migrants as “the victims of unfair (tabloid) media, which have racialised and demonised the migrants” (Bulat, 2017: 25). Conclusively, what used to be an attempt at both vilifying and romanticizing migrants has reached new depths (Romocea, 2014). Local emigration narratives underwent dramatic changes with the great recession of 2008 in the first place. For instance, large numbers of the Romanians working abroad were put out of business and on the screens of millions of Britons. Although “concerning intra-EU migration, the largest groups of migrants come from Romania (i.e., mainly worker migration)”, they settled traditionally for continental Europe (Jakob-Moritz Eberl, 2020: 14). The Romanians only reached British shores when the economic slump of 2008 and 2009 hit Italy, Spain, and France. Suddenly, interest in the Romanian underclass added significantly to the “semantic domain of migration” (Neagu et al., 2014: 202) in the UK mainstream media.

All of this is unfolding on screens that invite audiences to experience a visual narrative akin to class warfare, which sheds light on a culture of racism against “new Europeans in the UK” (Fox, 2013). As early as 2013, the Romanian ambassador to the UK argued that “the risk of racist attacks on eastern Europeans in Britain is rising” (Hope, 2013). For Romanian-language media, this migration coverage transmogrified large shares of their own audience living abroad into the great unwashed of Europe. In many ways, the COVID-19 outbreak has only made concerns over migration even more salient. Transnational workers have come to be branded as virus spreaders. The COVID-19 pandemic brought to a growing number of Romanian citizens the status of working poor. At home, 2020, an election year, recalled the country’s dark days from roughly a decade ago: from 2010 to 2012, another center-right coalition enforced a brutal austerity package, with 25% salary cuts in the public sector and severe reductions in social security benefits.

Notions of cultural diffusion brought about by the ready availability of online, English-language content adapted or translated by Romanian mainstream media have been largely overlooked. This paper aims to address this “lack of comparative studies dealing with European migration media discourses of the last decade(s)” as well as the “insufficient evidence on country-specific differences in discourses about intra-European [...] migration compared to migration discourses more generally” (Jakob-Moritz Eberl, 2020: 2). Given the context of Romania’s migration flows, media discrimination against one’s own audience (as ready-made phrases and adapted stories from English-speaking media) has never made it into research, despite its paradoxical currency in local news and opinion. This conjures up images of the inherently different Romanian expatriate, against the backdrop of migrants

being either glamorized or denounced (Benson, 2013). The Romanian “undocumented workers are the migrant proletariat” (Nail, 2015: 221) widely believed to have posed a deadly threat to EU transnational citizenship. In spring 2020, the same “migrant workers” (Crețan and Light, 2020) returned home in droves from a locked-down Western Europe to endanger their own country: it is likely that “COVID-19 occurred in Romania through case importation from Italy” (Hancean et al., 2020).

This study employs content analysis to analyze and interpret various media sources (e.g., news, opinion pieces, and videos) to spot discursive practices that structure main communication themes, as a means to trace likely diffusion patterns between English and Romanian-language coverage of Romanian-speaking migrants (self-identifying as Roma, Romanian or Moldovans). My qualitative analysis, even if somewhat descriptive, offers a re-reading of highly mediated migration content, consumed on the screen. Emphasizing the use value of translated/adapted English-language news and opinion, my argument covers how a broad range of English-speaking media reports on migration have shaped, over the last decade, emigration stereotyping in Romania. Although it can be argued that this paper is necessarily partial in selecting its material, a contrastive reading is informative of increasing systematic similarities between the media stories of immigration (the UK) and emigration (Romania) countries. This can show association, even if it should fail to prove causation. The media stories of Romanian-speaking audiences, both at home and abroad, have led to a self-righteous circle: the British tabloid logic made pro-Brexit views on immigration readily available to Romanian audiences, which, in turn, went mainstream in Romanian news and opinion. Eventually, this only reinforced stereotyping Romanian emigration from the perspective of populist media reports in immigration countries. So, the cycle went.

As always, cultural diffusion has everything to do with modes of transmission, beyond the presence of large Romanian communities living in the UK. The consumption of (audio)visual texts on migration is framed by narrative practices “through various media in a synchronized manner, with the screen playing a coordinating role” (Perez-Gonzales, 2011: 13). The criteria used for identifying the corpus of documents on which the analysis is performed are achieved by following a perceived dialectical relationship between English and Romanian-language media reports on emigration and immigration, respectively. Namely, I resort to news and opinion samples that highlight the process of translation and adaptation from English into Romanian, with a focus on Romanian migration. Far from being straightforward, the relation between the two national contexts is, nevertheless, likely. It delineates tropes and trends in migration storylines, aired online, over the last decade. Mainstream Romanian media have gradually appropriated migrant stock images originating in immigration countries such as the UK. The increase in the use of pejorative terms for Romanian citizens leaving their native country is prompted by ubiquitous screen media and widespread functional knowledge of English. Using online versions of British and Romanian news, I examine the reframing of such issues through British examples, prior to the Brexit agreement¹.

3. By Foreign Examples: Migrant-related Crises Facing Representation in Big Media Markets

The modes of transmission and circulation common to migration stories suggest that big media markets are instrumental in framing migration in the minor ones. English-language serial narratives about Romanian migrants feed off the perception that the Eastern European country is reliant on foreign remittances, mostly from undocumented migrants working in Western Europe. Their image discloses what Romanian citizenship used to stand for in the buildup for the Brexit referendum. In 2016, a notorious anti-immigration poster of Nigel Farage, at the time the leader of UKIP (UK Independence Party), incited to racial hatred by showing a mass of migrants heading to Germany, “with the only

¹ “Ziare.com”, a Romanian news aggregator, provides a view of the Romanian presence in the UK (<http://www.ziare.com/diaspora/romani-marea-britanie/stiri/>). www.ziare.com gives access to approximately 300 Romanian and British articles, starting with a piece in *The Sun*, published on 11th November 2012, 12:00 am, available at <http://www.ziare.com/diaspora/romani-marea-britanie/the-sun-valul-de-imigranti-din-romania-ameninta-sa-scurfunde-marea-britanie-1200960>. This is the Romanian translation of ‘The UK is much better than Romania. All my mates will come in 2014’; available at <https://www.thesun.co.uk/archives/news/1036548/the-uk-is-much-better-than-romania-all-my-mates-will-come-in-2014/>. Of particular interest to me are the online versions of *The Daily Mail*, *The Express*, or *The Telegraph*; quotations from Romanian are my translation.

prominent white person in the photograph obscured by a box of text” (Withers, 2019). In 2014, the same Farage argued that “any normal and fair-minded person would have a perfect right to be concerned if a group of Romanian people suddenly moved in next door” (*The Guardian*, 2014). The website of the digital radio station LBC (*Leading Britain’s Conversation*) is a case in point of how such visuals have been instrumentalized online, ever since migrants were “increasingly dehumanized in the British National Press” (Balch, 2016). Aversion to the Romanian nation, coupled with high esteem of the “wonderful Romanian people” (LBC, 2017), points to an authentic experience of racism on the part of some well-known Brexiters. Paradoxically, populist British politicians make the same point as highly skilled Romanians living in the UK, when interviewed by academic researchers: although the people are not necessarily poor and uneducated, Romania is not “a proper Western democracy” (LBC, 2017). This provides answers to questions regarding the lack of solidarity as most Romanians seem eager to point fingers themselves at fellow nationals and the Roma community (Stevens, 2003). Growing interest in immigration in the UK had everything to do with the first Romanian citizen (i.e., Victor Spirescu) to touch down at Luton airport (just after a travel ban was lifted, on January 1st, 2014). He gives a face to the low-skilled Eastern Europeans in the UK once and for good ².

Ultimately, the story of Romanian characters on screen is steeped in emotions connected to threats posed by racially charged immigration. For the most part, screen reporting on Romanian nationals working in the UK are faux observational documentaries, interviews, and news stories. What sets them apart from one another is their framing of migrants in relation to economic emergencies and to the spike in COVID-19 transmission. The public is asked either to cut migrants loose or consider their social use-value only. Such public concerns are conveyed in emotion-related expressions that call for a better understanding of the way small media markets appropriate the same reporting frames from immigration countries.

4. Facing up to Immigration

In the British news and opinion, immigration from Eastern Europe is framed in terms that express both notions of globalization and national self-identification. Words that pertain to European “integration of non-citizens” (Bommes and Geddes, 2000) are nevertheless long gone from headlines (BBC News, 2012). The best-case scenario is reporting on the way the “Romanian migrants in the UK cope with stigmatization” (Morosanu and Fox, 2013: 438). Ultimately, most migrant narratives endorse “an approach to the nation-state that depicts a nation and its migrants as fundamentally and essentially distinct” (Schiller and Faist, 2010: 25).

As Cheregi et al. (2015: 28) point out, “the British television often employs the same frames used by the British press”. Specifically, the British screen media looks at the “Romanian Other as the enemy” (Neagu et al., 2014: 211). With the 2020 pandemic and the migration flows it triggered, this is happening once again as “hundreds of Romanian fruit and veg pickers [were] to be flown in” (*The Telegraph*, 2020) the UK. Economic crises and the COVID-19 transmission have been accompanied by calls for increased state surveillance on “people with Romanian nationality [that] have become the second most common non-British population living in the UK” (BBC News, 2018). Their image is often incomplete because “Romanians tend to keep their heads down and are less likely to report [xenophobic abuse]” (BBC News, 2016). They embody yet another threat from the East, which never seems to grow old. The intersection between nation, race, and class is glaring in the coverage of specific events related to Romanian immigration. The overlap of ‘Roma’ and ‘Romanian’ in media discourses proves that racial ideas and practices are at play in the British discourse surrounding all citizens of Romania. News and opinion look at inexcusable public acts that come across as instances of typical Roma(nian) character. This is a reaction to a perceived assault on the British way of life (*The Telegraph*, 2011), perpetrated by rough sleepers camping in London’s parks (Dixon, 2013), i.e., by migrants alternatively designated as ‘Romanian’ and/or ‘Roma’. This underclass is believed to be responsible for their own way of life, one that entails petty theft, prostitution, and lying to get welfare payments. It follows that

² For a lengthy discussion on Victor Spirescu in British television documentaries see Cheregi, 2015.

the British stand to lose their livelihoods if they have not already³. On this account, the Eastern migrant proletariat is everything that is wrong with the EU. Particularly, the indigent Romanians have personified the evils of mobility rights across Europe “leading to suspicions that the much-vaunted EU principle of freedom of movement is being abused” (Beckford, 2015). In this respect, the film aired by *Channel 4*, “The Romanians Are Coming” (2015), puts together an assortment of media figures that convey influential Romanian identity narratives. It borrows most trappings of the docudrama: on-camera interviews with the migrants themselves, voice-overs, and undisclosed narrators. They all point to state-sponsored “discrimination against the extremely poor, especially the Roma” (Alston, 2015) in Romania. The message is conveyed through “the visual culture of the news” (Hill and Schwartz, 2020: 3) rather than newly found evidence. The Romanian underclass on British screens is the same, irrespective of their whereabouts. Explicitly, the alleged ethnic underpinnings of economic conflicts go against the understanding that the public has about a straightforward victim-perpetrator relationship. The screen narratives hint at the fact that Romanian “migrants mark, evaluate and rank difference in racialized ways to secure both social-psychological and material benefits” (Fox, 2013: 171). All they do is claim the above-mentioned benefits (*Express*, 2014). Most Romanians make the point that they are not Roma, even though they do come across as such (Cadwalladr, 2016). On screen, there is an attempt to make sense of a jumbled collection of Romanian characters and British settings. Image, sound, and written language deliver the story of the working poor, while making use of news pictures. The image of the migrant proletariat is saturated with many clues on possibly undocumented workers.

Nevertheless, there is no consensus on the nature of the image the Romanian citizens have in English-language news. The higher the degree of visual literacy the less likely it is that the public buys into the picture of the migrant proletariat taking advantage of the welfare state. This is part of a backlash against the migrant-blaming narrative in British politics and rightwing press (Jones, 2017), which started back in 2013 (Henley, 2013), and gained momentum long before the Brexit vote (Walsh, 2014). The framing of Romanian citizens added to the culture of surveillance and spectacle already in place across Europe. Media attention calls for excluding the Romanians and has effectively transformed them into a threat to the very fabric of British society. Mainstream Romanian media was soon to follow suit.

5. Facing up to Emigration

Emigration narratives in Romanian media look back on a cultural tradition in which migration is racially charged, as the travelling Roma people are a figment of historical imagination in Romania. In news and opinion, the “frequent overlaps of such categories as ‘Roma’ and ‘Romanian’ (Morosanu, 2007) are a long-standing feature of debates about the Roma living in Romania and the Romanians living abroad. However, the local press is known only for “emotional anti-racist and anti-discrimination message[s]” (Georgescu, 2011: 12) against Romanian rather than Roma migrants. Real and perceived emergencies brought about by the Romanian citizens abroad have a long history in post-communist Romania and the media has a great many news items to report on.

Free web content gives new meanings to the notion of foreign news and opinion. For the most part, the Romanian newsrooms do not reach out to shoot their own videos and pictures. This is consistent with the fact that, as far as the Romanian press is concerned “most of the articles (N = 67/41.4%) [on immigrants] had articles or programs from other media as the main source” (Marinescu and Balica, 2021: 8). Furthermore, translating content from English-language sources has become common in both news and social media. For example, a local version of the so-called “pandemic conspiracy theory” is debunked by pointing out that the “story of German and Spanish GPs who claim the COVID-19 pandemic [...] is part of a plan to take over the world [...] can be traced back to English-language sources already exposed as a hoax” (Simina, 2023). This is the case not only with media content but also with official reports that, for instance, look into modern slavery in the British construction sector (Mărăciue, 2023). In fact, depictions of Romanian rough sleepers in London have been circulating on

³ “Migrants DO take our jobs: Britons losing out to foreign workers, says official study” accessed February 28, 2023, <https://www.express.co.uk/news/uk/487645/Migrants-take-British-workers-jobs-says-official-study>; “Romanian and Bulgarian Workers Top 200,000 for First Time, Say Official Figures,” accessed February 28, 2023, <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/immigration/11987954/Romanian-and-Bulgarian-workers-top-200000-for-first-time-say-official-figures.html>.

Romanian-language websites and social media platforms for a considerable amount of time. Various examples can be found in Romanian online media. The photographs below, which date back to 2016, serve as illustrations of the sensational and exploitative translation and adaptation practices that are commonplace in Romanian tabloids.

Daily Mail⁴

Click.ro⁵

Both mainstream Romanian media and British tabloids portray Romanian speaking migrants in the UK as marginalized and deviant, reinforcing negative stereotypes. This consistent portrayal across various media platforms, including Romanian mainstream television stations' websites, contributes to the stigmatization of emigration in Romania:

Daily Mail⁶

StirileProTV⁷

⁴ Romanian rough sleepers in London double in a year | *Daily Mail Online* (no date). Available at: <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-3484941/Romanian-rough-sleepers-London-double-year-Ministers-warned-sharp-increase-homelessness-migrants.html> (Accessed: 8 November 2023).

⁵ În Londra, unul din cinci cerșetori este român (2016). Available at: <https://click.ro/actualitate/international/in-londra-unul-din-cinci-cersetori-este-roman-129975.html> (Accessed: 8 November 2023).

⁶ Constable, N. 2012 One-third of Big Issue sellers now Romanian: Job once reserved for Britain's homeless has been swamped by Eastern European immigrants. And guess what? Many of them have homes AND claim benefits, *Mail Online*. Available at: <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2090012/One-Big-Issue-sellers-Romanian-homes-AND-claim-benefits.html> (Accessed: 8 November 2023).

⁷ Europa ne arata iar cu degetul. Romanii au ajuns sa fure painea de la gura oamenilor strazii din UK (no date) *StirileproTV.ro*. Available at: <https://stirileproTV.ro/stiri/international/europa-ne-arata-iar-cu-degetul-romanii-au-ajuns-sa-fure-painea-de-la-gura-oamenilor-strazii-din-uk.html> (Accessed: 8 November 2023).

lthough the British and the Romanian framing of the migrant proletariat are converging, undocumented workers are less present in Romanian accounts of UK immigration. Instead, highly skilled Romanians make it on the screen to embody the virtues of liberal democracy. Academics, lawyers, or physicians, and their professional façade fix the gaze of the Romanian media at the expense of those who dream of low-wage jobs in London. The Romanian side attempts to expose scaremongering by the British government and the right-wing press, while working towards the development of a positive response from the public on East European immigration. The main argument that rages in Romanian media is whether young professionals, trained at public expense in state-funded universities, should be allowed to leave the country (*Hotnews*, 2019). As a principle, the Romanian news outlets argue that the UK's national health system – and the economy as a whole – benefit hugely from the influx of the Romanian skilled workers. The brain drain (*Romania Insider*, 2016) and, lately, brain regain are sides of the same coin (Adevarul, 2015). Emphasis on the consequences of Brexit for the UK and, specifically, for the foreign nationals already living here is a common frame of reference. Namely, “EU citizens will have to produce a photographic identification (ID card) in order to live and work in the UK” (Ziare.com, 2016a); “The worries of migrants living in the UK: a Romanian woman who backs Brexit” (Ziare.com, 2016b). For that matter, most Romanian news outlets prior and in the aftermath of Brexit followed the same editorial line: “Brexit: London declares war on immigration” (*Digi24*, 2016).

The British shaming the Romanian poor long found an answer in media campaigns originating in Romania. They used English to sway foreign audiences from the misrepresentation of Romania in British visual culture. A Romanian newspaper, *Gândul*, attempted to address an international public, rather than the local audiences. The campaign, “Why don't you come over” (*Gândul*, 2014), invited the British to see for themselves what Romania is like (Evans, 2013). The same Romanian quality newspaper, *Gândul*, launched on June 26, 2016, yet another campaign, with the self-explanatory title “Romanians Adopt Remainians”⁸. Acting the part of the European faithful, this time the Romanians offer shelter to the so-called remainers.

Lately, the COVID-19 outbreak brought the migrant poor once again into the limelight. Although major media players refrain from blunt statements like “the diaspora brought the plague and left” (National.ro, 2020), there is some consensus that this is actually the case. This prevents low-skill migrants from participating in the media space as anything else than agents of “criminality and economic poverty” (LSE blog, 2014). They are either subjects or agents of violence against themselves and others. Their media representations are a means to make sure that there is no direct challenge to stereotyping by foreign examples; they are presented in a sensationalized manner that plays on the lack of activism on their behalf. Conclusively, Romanian migrants are perceived as aliens both abroad and at home; they pose threats to nations, either through their absence or presence. The fact that the mainstream media of an emigration country delivers anti-migration messages, which have long gained traction in the public sphere (Momoc, 2016), can be construed as further proof that local attitudes towards migrants are changing for reasons extraneous to Romanian contexts.

6. The Effect of Im(E)migration in Romanian media

The process by which Romanian-language news purveyors had only their own socio-cultural contexts to choose and pick what aspects of expatriation to explore is now being shaped mostly by English-language content available online. With the transition of most news providers to online platforms (Florea, 2016), Romanian news websites have primarily drawn inspiration from Western models. Secondly, English has been the most taught foreign language in Romanian public schools since the collapse of communism (Bucur and Popa, 2015: 51). Thirdly, the large community of Romanian nationals working in the UK focused public attention on them. The cultural logic of English-language tabloids permeates stories of Romanian emigration.

The linear understanding of cultural diffusion, pervasive in the one-dimensional flows from British (tabloid) media at play in the articulation of Romanian narratives and stereotypical practices associated with im(e)migration, is necessarily oversimplifying. Yet, it is effective in accounting for collapsed and entwined English and Romanian-language news flows on and about both immigration and emigration. Online platforms help users gain a new understanding of how the media of immigration

⁸ <http://romaniansadoptremainians.gandul.info/>

countries break the news of migrant crises. Romanian–language audiences discover that the framing of mass departure from their country is promoted through the lens of foreign examples: the public consumption of ideas about emigration relates to attitudes and anxieties coming from abroad. Having your own people that leave the country, for good or only temporarily, as the target of prejudice (in the mainstream media of their home country) is revealing of how cultural meanings are constructed in Romanian contexts. Essentially, the notion of migration is not descriptive, and, even less, neutral. Its propagation in the media serves to reinforce conservative power structures, further entrenching the marginalized status of a Romanian underclass both in the UK and Romania. The media’s role in framing emigration is thus impacting on societal attitudes and, ultimately, on the lived experiences of migrants themselves.

Commonly, news and opinion come as screen narratives, often centered on negative emotions. Except for written language, the visuals of online communication can be salient to understanding the migration experience from an Eastern European perspective that internalizes Western values. As such, both emigration and immigration are all rolled into Romanian im(e)migration: local online news makes the most out of what search engines and social media already deemed suitable for British audiences the moment Eastern European migrants made their way to their shores. Designed to indulge the bias of its target audience, the cumulative effect on Romanian screen media is everything British spectators expected to get from their own news coverage, in the buildup to the Brexit negotiations. Overwhelmingly, bias against the working poor is the same both in the UK and Romania. Tailoring news to the public results in filter bubbles that, paradoxically, bring together populist defenders of exclusionary self-identification patterns, no matter where they happen to live across Europe. Public demand for narratives that project judgments from the British public on immigrants and, by association, on the Romanian poor, is currently a matter of fact in Romanian mainstream media. Romanian audiences go along with Britons living outside “areas with very high levels of immigration” (Daykin, 2016) that are prone to blame migrants for their own circumstances. This is consistent with the scapegoating of undocumented workers returning to Romania, from all over Europe, at the time of the COVID-19 crisis. Both British and Romanian audiences take part in constructing an idea of the migrant that builds on class hierarchy narratives.

The stories of screen media encompass both news and documentary forms. Their meaning is contingent on digital production and distribution. If read in sequence, both British and Romanian online news come across as serial narrative forms. Irrespective of medium or language, news on the Romanian working poor is essentially networked and convergent. In other words, news, and opinion, alongside archive photographs and film footage, mostly coming from the UK, are effectively validating and corroborating Romanian coverage of emigration.

The fact that Romanian audiences seem to learn about their own people living abroad mostly through translation and adaptation from foreign media relegates the Romanian migrants to one and the same alien condition: they are increasingly perceived as alien. This reading holds true in the way stereotypes around migrants, some of them originating in the UK, find currency in Romanian: the rift between the natives and the newcomers in their host country is now growing in their own home country, as a rift between returnees and local communities. These narratives tie in with wider concerns about better-off Romanian migrants that “frequently embraced the very stereotypes [i.e., British stereotypes] about fellow Romanian migrants, which they vocally condemned in other instances” (Bulat, 2017: 25).

Across European media markets, the Romanian im(e)migration is making vivid real and perceived linkages between East and West. English and Romanian-speaking audiences are sharing in the same emotion of impending disaster brought about by migrants. The visuals of the itinerant workers rely mostly on the iconography of class wars associated with racial minorities. They rely on high-impact graphics of male crowds entering one country or another, as well as rough sleeping in urban settings. Transnational laborers feature in media stories that hinge on national rather than transnational perspectives. Such visual frameworks, originally prevalent in Western Europe, have become ingrained in Romanian society as the country has grappled with the complexities of emigration under the influence of Western media portrayals. These narratives are now increasingly operationalized to make sense of the emerging reality of Romania as a host country for low-skilled Asian workers.

7. Conclusions

The British media's changing images and rhetoric about Romanian migration provides a snapshot not only of the evolving narrative production of Romanian-language migrants (self-identified as Roma, Romanian, or Moldovan), but also of English-language impact on the framing of migration in the Romanian language online press. Translation and adaptation have to a large extent directed vernacular reworkings and terminologies in Romanian relating to migration and its associated effects. These borrowed vocabularies significantly reflect ingrained, prevalent societal beliefs and senses, spreading misconceptions resulting in self-bias, linking labor immigration to society's detriment, hikes in unemployment, and plummeting domestic work-welfare standards to be experienced, paradoxically, in the Romanian job market, not only in the British one.

The media stories of Romanian-speaking migrants, both at home and abroad, have led to a self-righteous circle: the British tabloid logic made pro-Brexit views on immigration readily available to Romanian audiences, which, in turn, went mainstream in Romanian news and opinion. Eventually, converging views on the Romanian-speaking migrants reinforced stereotyping emigration from the perspective of populist media reports in immigration countries.

The analysis of media sources, including news, opinion pieces, and videos, has revealed a significant influence of English-language reporting on migration in shaping the perceptions and narratives surrounding emigration and immigration among Romanian-speaking audiences. The findings suggest that the transmission of cultural elements through media narratives has contributed to the construction of local narratives, cultural meanings, and stereotypical practices that impact national self-identification discourses in Romania. The research has addressed the lack of comparative studies on European migration media discourses and the insufficient evidence on country-specific differences in discourses about intra-European migration.

Media reports in English and Romanian on immigration and emigration exemplify the process of translation and adaptation between a prestige language (e.g., English) and a marginal one (e.g., Romanian). This process has highlighted trends and tropes in these migration stories, in both news and opinion pieces, over the past decade. Literally, mainstream Romanian media have begun to adopt stock images of migrants coming from immigration countries like the UK. The increase in the use of pejorative terms for Romanian citizens leaving the country can be due to translating and adapting English-language media and to widespread functional knowledge of English in post-communist Romania. This is consistent with findings on cultural convergence between emigration and immigration countries that involve potential influence on the home countries' norms and beliefs. However, in contrast to progressive norms and beliefs that are typically transferred to the home country (Docquier et al., 2017), the opposite appears to be true in this case.

The convergence of conservative and populist British media narratives with those of mainstream Romanian online press has played a significant role in shaping the Romanian discourses on migration. This framing has had a substantial impact in Romania, where similar narratives have gained traction, for instance, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and returning migrants. The use of these narratives reinforces misconceptions not only about Romanian-speaking migrants, but also about migration as a whole. The interconnectedness between English and Romanian-language media reports suggests that the circulation of migration narratives and stereotypes has created a self-reinforcing cycle, where British tabloid logic on immigration has become readily available to Romanian audiences; this outlook, in turn, has been mainstreamed in Romanian news and opinion. The cycle has perpetuated and reinforced Romanian self-perception from the perspective of populist media reports in immigration countries. Consequently, media convergence is shaping public discourses and influencing cultural attitudes towards migration. It does not only hinder a more nuanced understanding, but also reinforces barriers to societal inclusion and equitability for Romanian-speaking migrants, abroad and at home.

The conflation of mass emigration of highly educated professionals with unskilled or low-skilled migrants in the Romanian media has led to a limited and skewed understanding among the public, denying them a comprehensive view of complexities and nuances. Ultimately, the influence of English-language populist media, particularly in framing Romanian migrants as job stealers and benefit seekers, has reinforced negative stereotypes and discrimination against all the Romanian poor.

The large Romanian-speaking communities of low-skilled workers living in the UK, and the widespread use of English among the youth and the educated middle-aged, are part of the reason

English-language, open-access news platforms are likely to have been instrumental to the Romanian representation of both emigration and immigration. Conclusively, most news items on Romanian migrants set communication to the standard of immigration countries. This is the case with notions of social class and race as well. Unlike the paradigmatic 20th-century media, the screen narratives meet the demands of audiences known for high standards of living, both in the UK and Romania. Beyond national boundaries, online media are consistent with each other, with their public and their medium of circulation. Thus, they are blurring the lines of univocal Western or Eastern perspectives on migration and make the point of cultural diffusion from the English-speaking world. Romanian-language migration narratives are a site of struggle against oneself, with Western European nations in the background. This narrows views on migration to a single perspective and highlights mostly weak public service broadcasting. The limitations of this cross-national reading of migration narratives point to further investigation into how effects on peripheral media systems develop by foreign examples, mostly from big media markets.

The British online media's portrayal of Romanian migrants has, nevertheless, become more nuanced, offering increasingly diverse perspectives along the lines of binary oppositions between immigrants that are contributing to the economy and societal misfits challenging social norms. British and Romanian online media with progressive leanings have examined the complex issues of belonging, migration policy, and the social impact of migration, while also scrutinizing the accountability of those in power. The use of alternative images and more cautious language, as well as discourses on the politics of belonging and the impact of migration policies, have ultimately encouraged reflection on the social costs and political responsibility associated with migration. This has also highlighted entrenched divisions in British society and growing ones in Romania – yet another example of intra-European convergence. Future research should continue to explore these dynamics, as exemplified by migration narratives, and examine the potential for alternative perspectives, meant to challenge dominant discourses imported from big media markets.

Works Cited

- Adevarul. 2015. "Românii Stabiliți Peste Hotare Vor Învăța Cum Să Investească În România Prin Programul 'Re>patriot'| Adevarul.Ro" <https://adevarul.ro/economie/romanii-stabiliti-peste-hotare-vor-invata-cum-sa-1618853.html>. (Accessed March 3, 2023)
- Alston, Ph. 2015. *End-of-mission statement on Romania, by Professor Philip Alston, United Nations Human Rights Council Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights*, OHCHR. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/statements/2015/11/end-mission-statement-romania-professor-philip-alston-united-nations-human> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Andersen, M.L., Taylor, H.F. and Logio, K.A. 2014. *Sociology: The Essentials*. Cengage Learning.
- Andreouli, E. et al. 2019. "Everyday Cosmopolitanism in Representations of Europe among Young Romanians in Britain". Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0038038518777693> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Balch, A. Balabanova. E. 2016. "Ethics, Politics and Migration: Public Debates on the Free Movement of Romanians and Bulgarians in the UK, 2006–2013." *Politics* 36, no. 1: 19–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9256.12082>.
- Barret, D. 2015. "Romanian and Bulgarian workers top 200,000 for the first time, say official figures", *The Telegraph*. Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/immigration/11987954/Romanian-and-Bulgarian-workers-top-200000-for-first-time-say-official-figures.html> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- BBC News. 2014a. "Nigel Farage attacked over Romanians 'slur'", 18 May. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-27459923> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- BBC News. 2014b. "Miliband: Too Little Done to Integrate UK Society - BBC News", Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/av/uk-politics-20723524> (Accessed February 28, 2023)
- BBC News. 2016a. "Brexit vote: Romanians anxious about future in UK", 5 July. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-politics-eu-referendum-36704783> (Accessed October 29, 2023)

- BBC News. 2018. “Romanian becomes second most common non-UK nationality”, 24 May. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-44235867> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Beciu, C. et al. (2017) “Media engagement in the transnational social field: discourses and repositionings on migration in the Romanian public sphere”, *Critical Discourse Studies*, 14(3), pp. 256–275. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17405904.2017.1284682>
- Beckford, M. 2015. “Romanians EIGHT times as likely to be jailed here as Britons”, *Mail Online*. Available at: <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2963368/Romanians-EIGHT-times-likely-jailed-Britons.html> (Accessed October 29, 2023).
- Benson, R. 2013. “Shaping Immigration News: A French-American Comparison”. *Cambridge University Press*
- Bommes, M. and Geddes, A. 2000. *Immigration and Welfare: Challenging the Borders of the Welfare State*. Oxon: Psychology Press.
- Bucur, N. F. and Popa, O. R. 2015. “The Evolution of the English Subject Curriculum in Romanian Primary and Lower Secondary Education.” *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 203 (August): 50–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.08.258>.
- Bulat, A., 2017. “We are not Tolerant as a Nation, but we want Others to Tolerate us: Romanians’ Experiences of Discrimination and their Attitudes Towards British People”, *Euxeinos*, 22 / 2017, pp. 25-43
- Cadwalladr, C. 2016. “Romania: hellhole or country of romance and mystery?”, *The Guardian*, 20 March. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/mar/20/romania-hellhole-or-mysterious-romanticism-europe-uncovered> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Cheregi, B-F et al. 2015. “The Visual Framing of Romanian Migrants in the National Press: A Social Semiotic Approach,” *Romanian Journal of Journalism and Communication*, no. 2 (2015): 12–24
- Crețan, R. and Light, D. 2020 “COVID-19 in Romania: transnational labour, geopolitics, and the Roma “outsiders””, *Eurasian Geography and Economics*, 61(4–5), pp. 559–572. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15387216.2020.1780929>
- Cross, S. 2014. ‘Mad and bad media: Populism and pathology in the British tabloids’, *European Journal of Communication*, 29(2), pp. 204–217. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323113516734>
- Dawar, A. (2014) “Migrants DO take our jobs: Britons losing out to foreign workers, says”, *On Express.co.uk*. Available at: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/uk/487645/Migrants-take-British-workers-jobs-says-official-study> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Daykin, J. (2016) “Could social media be tearing us apart?”, *The Guardian*, 28 June. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/media-network/2016/jun/28/social-media-networks-filter-bubbles> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Digi24. 2016. *Brexit | Londra declară război imigranților*. Available at: <https://www.digi24.ro/stiri/externe/ue/brexit-londra-declara-razboi-imigrantilor-581679> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Dixon, H. 2013. “UK’s Roma population much higher than previously thought”, *The Telegraph*. Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/immigration/10416099/UKs-Roma-population-much-higher-than-previously-thought.html> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Docquier, F. et al. 2017. “Do Emigrants Self-Select Along Cultural Traits? Evidence from the MENA Countries.” *International Migration Review*, 54, pp. 388 - 422. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0197918319849011>
- Dolea, A. 2018. “The Impact of Migration on the Construction of Romania’s Country Image: Two Intersecting Public Problems,” in *Debating Migration as a Public Problem: National Publics and Transnational Fields*, ed. Camelia Beciu, Mălina Ciocea, Irina Diana Mădroane, and Alexandru I. Cărlan, Bern/New York: Peter Lang.
- Evans, N. 2013. ““Come to Romania, Our Women Look like Kate and Pippa’: Newspaper Launches Campaign against UK Portrayal of Immigrants,” – *Mirror Online* (no date). Available at: <https://www.mirror.co.uk/news/weird-news/kate-middleton-gandul-romanian-newspaper-1569564> (Accessed June 21, 2023)
- Express. 2014. ““Thank You Britain,’ Roma Gypsy Boasts UK Benefits System Built His £60k

- Mansion” *Express.Co.Uk*. Available at: <https://www.express.co.uk/news/uk/544816/Roma-Gypsy-Migrant-Boasts-Free-Money-Benefits-System-Mansion> (Accessed February 28, 2023).
- Florea, I. C. 2016. “Romanian Media Industry. A Look Back at Responses to Crises and Disruptive Changes”, *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series XVI*, no. 2, pp. 209–14.
- Fox, J. E. 2013. “The uses of racism: whitewashing new Europeans in the UK”, *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 36(11), pp. 1871–1889. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2012.692802>.
- LSE. 2014. “How has the UK national press described Bulgarians and Romanians?”, British Politics and Policy at LSE, 26 August. Available at: <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/politicsandpolicy/how-uk-press-describe-bulgarians-and-romanians/> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- LBC. 2017. “‘You’re A Racist’: LBC Caller Hurls Insults at Nigel Farage in Fiery Debate” (no date) LBC. Available at: <https://www.lbc.co.uk/radio/presenters/nigel-farage/nigel-farage-european-army-point-of-no-return/> (Accessed October 19, 2023)
- Gândul. 2017. “We walk the talk and even offer the Brits some job opportunities! Why don't you come over?” Available at: <http://whydontyoucomeover.gandul.info/> (Accessed October 1, 2018)
- Gândul and GMP Advertising/Webstyler. 2017. “Europe Must Remain United: If You Are Romanian Adopt a Remainer, If You’re British Apply to Be Adopted!”, 2017, *Romanians Adopt Remainians*. Gândul, <http://romaniansadoptremainians.gandul.info/>
- Georgescu, C. M. 2011. “Stereotypes, migrants and the media: an analysis of the Romanian press on migration”, *Revista de Științe Politice*, 29, 52–65.
- Hâncean, M-G et al. 2020. “Early spread of COVID-19 in Romania: imported cases from Italy and human-to-human transmission networks” *Royal Society Open Science* (no date). Available at: <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsos.200780> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Henley, J. 2013. “Romania and Bulgaria: ‘If people go to Britain, of course it’s to contribute’”, *The Guardian*, 26 December. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/dec/26/romania-bulgaria-britain-eu-benefit-restrictions> (Accessed October 7, 2022)
- Hill, J.E. and Schwartz, V.R. 2020. *Getting the Picture: The Visual Culture of the News*. New York: Routledge
- Hope, C. 2013. “Romanians at risk of attacks, warns envoy”, *The Telegraph*. Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/law-and-order/9886247/Romanians-at-risk-of-attacks-warns-envoy.html> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Horton, H. 2020. “Hundreds of Romanian fruit and veg pickers to be flown in as travel restrictions leave farms short of staff”, *The Telegraph*, 15 April. Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/2020/04/15/hundreds-romanian-fruit-veg-pickers-flown-travel-restrictions/> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Hotnews. 2020. “Plecarea ‘creierelor’: Este fiscalitatea o soluție pentru această problemă?”, *HotNews.ro*. Available at: <https://economie.hotnews.ro/stiri-cariere-23303806-plecarea-creierelor-este-fiscalitatea-solutie-pentru-aceasta-problema.htm> (Accessed October 3, 2021)
- Jakob-Moritz Eberl et al., 2020. “European Media Migration Report: How Media Cover Migration and Intra-EU Mobility in Terms of Saliency, Sentiment and Framing”. Available at: <https://www.reminder-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/REMINDER-D8.3.pdf> (Accessed July 10, 2022)
- Jones, O. 2017. “Migrants are always the scapegoats. But now they’re taking on Ukip’s lies”, *The Guardian*, 16 February. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2017/feb/16/migrants-scapegoats-ukip-compelling-stories-win-over-xenophobes> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Marinescu, V. and Balica, E. (2021) “New media clues and old journalistic habits: Representing the refugees in Romanian media”, *Journalism*, 22(4), pp. 1048–1066. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884918810038>
- Mădroane, I. D. 2012. “Romanian Migrants in the British Press: A Post-EU Accession Analysis,” *Revista Romană de Comunicare și Relații Publice XIV*, no. 4 (2012): 103–23
- Mădroane, I. D. 2018. “Romanian immigration in the British newspapers: engaging audiences

- during the Brexit referendum campaign”, in *Debating Migration as a Public Problem*, Camelia Beciu, Mălina Ciocea, Irina Diana Mădroane and Alexandru I. Cârlan, (eds), New York: Peter Lang Publishing.
- Mărăcine, A. 2023. “500 de muncitori români, bătuți și exploatați în Marea Britanie. Grupul infracțional din România a făcut milioane de lire sterline timp de 10 ani”, *Libertatea*. Available at: <https://www.libertatea.ro/stiri/500-de-romani-muncitori-in-constructii-in-marea-britanie-au-fost-batuti-si-cazati-in-conditii-mizere-grupul-infractional-din-romania-a-facut-milioane-de-lire-din-exploatarea-lor-4619522> (Accessed: 8 November 2023).
- Momoc, A. 2016. “Political Angles in The Romanian Online Media About the Refugees’ Crisis and Islam. Traian Băsescu Case,” *Europolity – Continuity and Change in European Governance* - New Series 10, no. 1, pp. 1–16.
- Morosanu, L. 2007. “Back to Europe? Framing Romania’s Accession to the European Union in the United Kingdom.” *Migrationonline.cz*, 1-12, 9. Available at: <http://migrationonline.cz/en/back-to-europe-framing-romania> (Accessed May 1, 2019)
- Morosanu, L. and Fox, Jon E, 2013. “‘No smoke without fire’: Strategies of coping with stigmatised migrant identities”. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1468796813483730> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Moroșanu, L. 2015. “Researching Coethnic Migrants: Privileges and Puzzles of ‘Insiderness’”, *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 16(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-16.2.2371>
- National.ro, “Îmbolnăvesc Bătrânii de Pneumonie, ca Să-i Treacă Pe Lista COVID”. Available at: <https://www.national.ro/social/imbolnavesc-batranii-de-pneumonie-ca-sa-i-treaca-pe-lista-COVID-693905.html> (Accessed March 3, 2023).
- Nail, Th. 2015. *The Figure of the Migrant*, Stanford University Press.
- Neagu, M. et al., 2014. “Metaphor and Self/Other Representations. A Study on British and Romanian Headlines on Migration”, *Metaphor and Intercultural Communication*, Musolff, A., MacArthur, F. and Pagani, G. (eds.), Bloomsbury Academic. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781472593610>
- Pantiru, S. A. et al. 2014. “The Acculturation Process of Romanian Immigrants in the UK”. *Reinvention: An International Journal of Undergraduate Research*, 7.1.
- Pencheva, D. 2020. “Stealing jobs and benefits: Bulgarians and Romanians in British news Media”, 28-62, *Changes and Challenges of Cross-Border Mobility within the European Union*, Thomsen T. L. (ed.), <https://www.peterlang.com/document/1111374>
- Pérez-González, L. 2011. “Audiovisual translation”, in *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*, 13-20, Baker, M. et al. (eds.), London: Routledge.
- Romania Insider. 2016. “IMF: Brain drain effects are visible in Romania”, *Romania Insider*. Available at: <https://www.romania-insider.com/imf-brain-drain-effects-visible-romania> (Accessed November 29, 2023)
- Romocea, O. 2014. “Ethics and Emotions: A Migrant Researcher Doing Research among Romanian Migrants”, *Sociological Research Online*, 19(4), pp. 176–189. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.3489>
- The Guardian. 2014. “Ukip’s Nigel Farage defends Romanian ‘criminals’ comment”, *The Guardian*, 17 May. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2014/may/17/ukip-xenophobic-not-racist-eric-pickles> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- The Telegraph. 2011. “David Cameron: migration threatens our way of life”. Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/immigration/8449324/David-Cameron-migration-threatens-our-way-of-life.html> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- “The Romanians Are Coming”. 2015. All 4. James Bluemel. Available at: <http://www.channel4.com/programmes/the-romanians-are-coming> (Accessed: 29 October 2023).
- Schiller, N. G. and Faist, T. 2010. *Migration, Development, and Transnationalization: A Critical Stance*. Berghahn Books.
- Simina, C. 2020. “Povestea Cu ‘Medicii Din Germania Și Spania’ Care Declară Că ‘Pandemia a Fost

- Planificată’ e o Făcătură Plagiată Din Limba Engleză,” *PressOne*. Available at <https://pressone.ro/povestea-cu-medicii-din-germania-si-spania-care-declara-ca-pandemia-a-fost-planificata-e-o-facatura-plagiata-din-limba-engleza> (Accessed February 28, 2023).
- Stevens, D. 2003. The Migration of the Romanian Roma to the UK: A Contextual Study, *European Journal of Migration and Law*, Volume 5 Issue 4. Available at: https://brill.com/view/journals/emil/5/4/article-p439_1.xml (Accessed: 29 October 2023).
- Vathi, Z. and Trandafoiu, R. 2020. ‘EU nationals in the UK after BREXIT: Political engagement through discursive awareness, reflexivity and (in)action’, *Journal of Language and Politics*, 19(3), pp. 479–497. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1075/jlp.19028.vat> (Accessed February 28, 2023)
- Walsh, J. 2014. ‘Romanians and Bulgarians in the UK react to immigration furore’, *The Guardian*, Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2014/jan/03/romanians-and-bulgarians-in-the-uk-react-to-immigration-furore> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Withers, M. 2019. “Breaking point: The brilliant poster showing the real threats to the country”, *The New European*. Available at: <https://www.theneweuropean.co.uk/brexit-news-poster-showing-the-real-threats-to-the-country-42858/> (Accessed October 29, 2023)
- Ziare.com, 2016a “Cetatenii Din Statele UE Vor Avea Nevoie de Documente Speciale Pentru a Locui Si Munci in Marea Britanie,” Accessed March 3, 2023, <https://ziare.com/europa/marea-britanie/cetatenii-din-statele-ue-vor-avea-nevoie-de-documente-speciale-pentru-a-locui-si-munci-in-marea-britanie-1445620>
- Ziare.com, 2016b “Framantarile Imigrantilor Din Marea Britanie: Ce Spune o Romanca Din UK Care Sustine Brexit,” Accessed March 3, 2023, <https://ziare.com/brexit/marea-britanie/framantarile-imigrantilor-din-marea-britanie-ce-spune-o-romanca-din-uk-care-sustine-brexit-1435397>
- Yar, M. 2012. “Crime, media and the will-to-representation: Reconsidering relationships in the new media age”, *Crime, Media, Culture*, 8(3), pp. 245–260. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741659012443227>.